

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

PROJECT ACRONYM: **RECAP**

PROJECT NUMBER: **693171**

PROJECT FULL TITLE: **Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP**

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER & NAME:

WP.1 Project Management

DELIVERABLE NUMBER & NAME:

D.1.7 Report on Advisory Board meetings (2)

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171.

Grant Agreement Number: 693171

Acronym: RECAP

Project Full Title: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

Start Date: 01/05/2016

Duration: 30 months

Project URL: www.recap-h2020.eu

Deliverable Number & Name: D.1.7 Report on Advisory Board meetings (2)

Work Package Number & Name: WP.1 Project Management

Date of Delivery: 30/6/2017

Contractual:

Actual: 30/6/2017

30/6/2017

Nature: Report

Dissemination Level: Public

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DOCUMENT HISTORY:

Versions	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	12/6/2017	Draft	Draft for review	DRAXIS
2.0	21/6/2017	Draft	Review Feedback	INTIA
3.0	30/6/2017	Final	Final Version	DRAXIS

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1. Executive summary

This report aims to introduce the new members of the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) and outline the most important points discussed during the 2nd EEAB meeting of RECAP. The members of the EEAB were contacted via Internet using WebEx. This deliverable summarises the main points of the discussions and the recommendations that these experts have provided to the project.

Regarding the structure of the current document, Chapter 2 provides a short introduction of the EEAB role within the RECAP project, while Chapter 3 presents the changes made on the board from M4 to M14. The meetings held during this period between members of the EEAB and the RECAP partners are presented in Chapter 4, and finally, some of the most important recommendations of the members of the EEAB to RECAP are summarised in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 briefly presents the whole EEAB up to the present day.

2. Introduction

Besides the communication between the RECAP members, the EEAB maximizes the visibility and relevance of the research and outcomes conducted in the RECAP project. In order to achieve that, an EEAB has early been established in the project (M4) to provide help to focus the RECAP project on the most related challenges, ensure the outputs are validated and provide recommendations during all the project's phases.

The RECAP EEAB consists of independent external experts in key areas and includes experts from the agricultural spectrum, as well as from different types of organisations such as consultant companies, public institutions and companies related to Satellite Remote Sensing.

The inclusion of an EEAB to the RECAP project is considered as an important matter for the success of the project and hence it has been initiated from the early stages of the project and will be a constant procedure.

3. Update of the EEAB list

The EEAB list may be updated throughout the duration of the project in a case an additional need for consultation will occur. Hence, as the RECAP EEAB members are people who are engaged with various activities in their fields of expertise, they may change position during the project. The RECAP EEAB is enhanced with 2 more members. A short description of the qualifications of the EEAB members is presented below:

Prodromos Kalaitzis has changed position

Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis is Senior Policy Advisor on policies related to agri-food cooperatives and Producer Organisations. Mr. Kalaitzis is of Greek Nationality, and a business economist with post graduate studies on agricultural economics. He has worked for more than a decade as a researcher on agricultural cooperatives at the Netherlands Institute for Cooperative Entrepreneurship and at Wageningen University in the Netherlands on agri-food marketing and food supply chains. During the last decade he has lobbied in Brussels for Copa-Cogeca (the European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives organisation), as a cooperative expert and senior policy adviser on agri-cooperatives, internal market and EU Budget. He is currently active as a policy consultant in Greece, as well as on international level, in projects on the development of agri-food business and institutional structures.

Clement Atzberger joined the RECAP EEAB

Clement Atzberger is Full Professor and Head of the Institute of Surveying, Remote Sensing and Land Information (IVFL) of BOKU University in Vienna, Austria. He is a remote sensing & GIS expert with +20 years overall project experience in land use / land cover classification and environmental monitoring using very high to low resolution satellite imagery. He obtained his PhD in crop growth modeling and remote sensing data assimilation. His technical experience includes the development and inversion of physically based radiative transfer models, the use of machine learning techniques for classification tasks as well as the estimation of vegetation biophysical variables such as LAI. He is also an expert for proper RS data pre-processing (such as atmospheric corrections) and time series analysis (incl. land surface phenology).

Alan Matthews joined the RECAP EEAB

Alan Matthews is Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy at Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland. His research interests include the areas of agricultural policy and modelling, applied trade policy and WTO rules affecting agriculture and food security. He has published widely and has undertaken commissioned studies for the European Commission, the European Parliament, the Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations and the OECD in these areas. He is a past-President of the European Association of Agricultural Economists and is currently a member of Ireland's Climate Change Advisory Council. He is a regular contributor to the blog capreform.eu on issues relating to the EU's Common Agricultural Policy.

The full list of the EEAB members can be found in Chapter 6, while short CVs of all members are also provided in the [RECAP website](#).

4. Meeting Overview

The scope of the EEAB meetings was to inform EEAB members about the RECAP project and the challenges the consortium faces, and to offer the RECAP consortium the chance to elicit some initial crucial recommendations for the project's implementation.

Clement Atzberger

The meeting was held among Clement, Dimitrios Petalios (CREVIS), Stelios Kotsopoulos (DRAXIS) and Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia (DRAXIS) via WebEx and after the participants were notified, the meeting recording was started.

The meeting was held on 23rd of March 2017 and it lasted for approximately 40 minutes. At first, Dimitris welcomed Clement and thanked him for his participation on the EEAB. Following the presentation of the RECAP project highlighting the problem, the objectives, the main components of the envisioned platform and the key points of its future implementation, more focus was placed on the remote sensing and how RECAP will facilitate this component to enhance the monitoring of farmers' compliance with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Moreover, alternative remote sensing providers and collaborations were introduced for further capability expansion and exploitation.

Alan Matthews

The meeting was held among Alan Matthews, Dimitrios Petalios (CREVIS), Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM) and Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia (DRAXIS) via WebEx and after the participants were notified, the meeting recorded was started.

The meeting was held on 8th of February 2017 and it lasted for approximately 40 minutes. At first, Dimitris welcomes Alan and thanked him for his participation on the EEAB. Then Ifigeneia presented the project highlighting the key points of its future implementation. Moreover, she presented the problem, the objectives of the RECAP project and the main components of the envisioned platform. Manolis briefly described the role and the obligations of the Advisory Board within the project.

The main issues that addressed during the meeting were the farmers' and Paying Agencies' perspective towards the use of ICT solutions for monitoring the compliance to the CAP standards, their general attitude toward the Cross Compliance rules and the adaptability of the platform to adjust to the forthcoming changes of the Agricultural Policy.

5. Results and recommendations

Name	Recommendations and Suggestions	RECAP Actions
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should take into consideration the possibility of a collaboration with JRC.	RECAP has identified some stakeholders in the Monitoring Agricultural Resources (MARS) and several Policy Officers interlinking with the MARS' activities. WP5 – D5.4
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should organise a meeting with JRC in order to discuss EU Policy issues regarding the agricultural sector.	RECAP will organise a Policy session during the first review meeting in Brussels and will invite members of JRC.
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should involve JRC as soon as possible in order to clarify their expectations and develop a product compliant with the EU regulations.	RECAP has started communication with JRC in order to involve them to the EEAB and keep up with imminent EU Policy adaptations. WP1 – D1.8
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should take into consideration the possibility to collaborate with EODC, which provides EO data.	RECAP may contact EODC in order to establish a connection for future collaboration. WP5 – D5.4
Alan Matthews	RECAP should have specific modules for each of the pilots countries due to the different needs generated from the cross compliance rules. These modules should be easily adapted to existing systems.	RECAP platform will be customised for each of the five pilot countries including different software components for some of them. WP3 – D3.3
Alan Matthews	Farmers feels anxious by the risk of making mistakes trying to comply with the regulations. RECAP should take into consideration this and be a useful tool for farmers.	RECAP platform will have a customised cross compliance rules checklist which will be created after the farmer has edited the necessary details in his/ her profile.
Alan Matthews	Farmers feels frustrated by the rules complexity and diversity. RECAP should try to simplify the procedure of compliance.	RECAP will create an e-learning component with which farmers will be able to watch videos related to the use of RECAP platform, the inspections, the cross compliance rules. The content of the video will be defined from each Paying Agency.

6. List of members of EEAB

Name	Organisation & expertise
Prodromos Kalaitzis	Policy consultant in projects on the development of agri-food business and institutional structures
Peter Fane	Eurinco, European policy consultants, Agriculture, Rural development and renewable energy
Socrates Socratous	Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	FORTH, Foundation for Research and Technology- Hellas
Clement Atzberger	BOKU University in Vienna, Austria, Full Professor and Head of the Institute of Surveying, Remote Sensing and Land Information (IVFL)
Alan Matthews	Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland, Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy